

Unlocking the Link Between Calculated Risk-Taking and Marketing Performance of Small Enterprises in Ekiti State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT: Calculated risk is a foreseeable risk that can be estimated in advance with possibility of high return in the face of high level of uncertainty. Based on this, the study investigated the link between calculated risk-taking by small business owners in Ekiti State, Nigeria and their marketing performance. Specifically, the study examined the link between entering new market, adoption of new technology, financial risk, new venture creation, source of funding, credit facilities, and marketing performance of small enterprises in Ekiti State, Nigeria. The study was conducted using descriptive survey research design. Using systematic and purposive sampling techniques, eight (8) local government areas (LGAs) out of the sixteen LGAs in Ekiti state, Nigeria were selected for the study. These LGAs were selected because they have the highest number of registered small businesses in the State. With the aid of proportionate sampling technique, 99, 35, 37, 29, 34, 62, 23 and 64 small businesses were selected from the eight previously selected LGAs respectively, totaling 383. Primary data used for the study were collected with the aid of semi-structured questionnaire and analysed using means, standard deviation and multiple regression. Findings from the study revealed a significant positive relationship between calculated risk-taking and marketing performance of small businesses in Ekiti State, Nigeria. The study concluded that a unit increase in calculated risk-taking led to a significant increase in marketing performance of small enterprises in Ekiti State, Nigeria.

KEYWORDS: Calculated Risk-Taking, Marketing Performance, Market Share, Customer Satisfaction, Small Enterprises.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The success of an organization is determined in part by its performance in the sector in which it operates. The performance of an organization marks the outcome of its strategies, skills, tools, techniques and other resources deployed to achieve its objectives. Every organization is borne to achieve a specific purpose or objective, the extent to which such is achieved is determined by how well it served its customers and the goodwill enjoyed. Marketing performance is the extent to which an organization is able to retain its customers, maintain good customer relationships, meets customer expectation, and increase its sales volume. Measuring the marketing performance of a small business is difficult and remains a question yet unanswered. Being an entrepreneur, starting a new venture, entering a new market, sourcing for funds, hiring and retaining the talents, and determining appropriate distribution strategy and pricing, all involve risks. Such risks must be well understood to determine its nature and type. Entrepreneurial risk-taking is a strategic posture of entrepreneurs that demonstrates their preference for pursuing opportunities where the probability of success is uncertain but the potential benefits are significant (Samuel & Samuel, 2022). Entrepreneurial risk-taking essentially refers to the willingness of business owners to act under uncertainty with the expectation of achieving growth, profitability and competitive advantage.

It is important to note that it's almost impossible to start a new venture or launch a new product/service without some level of risk. In Nigeria, due to harsh and unfavourable economic condition the success of starting a new venture or launching a new product is slim and the risk of failure is considerably high hence the answer is to take calculated risk. Calculated risk-taking is an evidence-based risk-taking. It is a risk-taking that is based on experience, observation, experiment, assessment, estimation or analysis of trends. Based on this, it is imperative to determine the extent to which small business owners particularly in Ekiti State, Nigeria take calculated risk and how this spur their marketing performance.

Though there are plethora of studies on risk-taking and performance of small businesses generally only a few had made attempt at investigating the possible effect of it on marketing performance of small businesses in Nigeria and in particular Ekiti State. In Nigeria, using a population of 354 small and medium enterprises (SMEs), Baba and Thiong (2019) conducted an investigation on the impact of risk-taking on performance of small and medium enterprises in Plateau State. The results of the correlation and

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regression analyses indicated that risk-taking had a positive but insignificant effect on the performance of SMEs in Nigeria. In Bayelsa State, Ajor and Nwaiwu (2020) conducted a study investigating the impact of a calculated risk-taking mindset on the organizational sustainability of SMEs. Findings from the data analysis using Spearman Rank Order Correlation Coefficient, revealed a positive and significant relationship between the calculated risk-taking mindset and organizational sustainability. Apart from Nigeria, Jeje (2020) conducted a study assessing the performance of bakeries in Tanzania in connection with risk-taking. The outcome of the in-depth interviews with bakery owners/managers across Tanzania using principal component factor analysis revealed a significant positive contribution of calculated risk-taking to the performance of bakeries in Tanzania. However, despite the above studies, it is yet to be established the link between calculated risk-taking and marketing performance of small businesses in Ekiti State, Nigeria. Majority of the previous studies had concentrated efforts at assessing the effects of risk-taking on the general performance of SMEs. This study takes a step further by seeking to unlock the link between calculated risk-taking and the marketing performance of small businesses in Ekiti State, Nigeria.

2.0 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Calculated Risk-taking

A calculated risk is a carefully well-thought-out decisions that expose an entrepreneur or business owner to a certain level of personal and financial risks that is compensated for by a reasonable prospect of benefit. According to Masterclass (2021), assessing whether or not a risk is worth it involves careful cost-benefit analysis. This implies that venturing into a new business involves risk and before resources are committed to it requires carrying out a thorough analysis of it in relation to the available resources to determine if it's profitable. Calculated risk-taking entails undertaking bold actions in the face of uncertainty such as entering new markets, starting new ventures with high level of uncertainty and accessing loans from unpredictability source in a keenly competitive business environment.

According to Ogueze, et al. (2017), calculated risk-taking is the deliberate allocation of funds to projects with the potential for high returns but also entails a possibility of significant failure. Olanrewaju (2020) commenting on calculated risk-taking and exploring it from market dynamics point of view perceived it as the capacity of small enterprises to carefully embrace the risk of entering a new market for expansion. In this context, companies exhibit a positive outlook, even though they cannot precisely predict future events in the business world. They continuously explore, search for, and capitalize on new opportunities to gain a first-mover advantage and reap the benefits of innovation (Jorg & Christoph, 2020). On a business level, Ogunsoji and Kayode (2020) identify three fundamental types of risk: business risks (linked to entering new markets or supporting unproven technologies), financial risks (involving heavy borrowing or committing significant resources for growth), and the financial exposure required, along with the risk/return profile of the new venture. Setyawatti, et al. (2020) perceived risk-taking as the conscious allocation of resources to projects with the potential for high returns but also acknowledging the possibility of significant failure.

Risk-taking is an entrepreneurial attributes that demonstrates small business owner's predisposition to pursue opportunities where the prospect of success is uncertain. According to Samuel and Samuel (2022) entrepreneurial risk-taking refers to the willingness of a business owner to act in the face of uncertainty with the hope of making profit, achieving growth and competitive advantage. Risk-taking therefore reflects the mental orientation of small business owners to view challenges as opportunities and uncertainty as a drive to strategic decision-making with the aim of making a business. Taking risks is a demonstration of small business owners' conviction that progress, expansion and profit are possible by venturing into a new business and un-entered market. Supporting this view, Adim and Bassey (2022) averred that small enterprises' entrepreneurial risk-taking is a defining characteristics that differentiates successful firms from those that remain stagnant. Based on this, risk-taking is the practical demonstration of commitment to growth, innovation and survival in competitive markets where certainty rarely exists.

2.2 Marketing Performance

Generally, performance is perceived as outcomes or success arising from organization's efforts.

Performance can be considered as the outputs, outcomes or results derived from various processes, production, services and efforts of the organization that allow for comparison against a set goal, benchmark or standard that may be expressed in monetary and non-monetary terms. In essence therefore, according to Ogunsoji and Kayode (2020) performance represents the end result of activities which encompasses the actual outcomes of strategic management process. It is the end results derived from production processes and service activities of the organisation whether expressed in monetary terms or not.

Ranasinghe, et al. (2019) interpreted performance from two distinct perspectives: as a means of achieving an outcome and as the outcome itself. They elaborated that performance encompasses a series of activities or actions directed towards attaining a desired outcome or result within a specific timeframe. Furthermore, they emphasized that the end result could also be labeled as performance. Performance therefore is the ability to recognize the concluding results of organization's actions. It explains the outcomes of an organization following the effective utilization of various resources or the course of action taken.

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Based on the above, marketing performance is explained as external efficacy measure for an organization (Usani et al., 2021). To Usani and Eko (2021), marketing performance is an economic measure of production efficiency in relation to customer retention, customer relationships, customer satisfaction, and the firm's increase in sales volume. Etuk et al. (2022) explained marketing performance using four major dimensions of internal processes, customer, financial and innovativeness.

Measuring marketing performance has recently attracted more attention from both researchers and industry professionals (Sampson et al., 2022; Etuk et al., 2022). Marketing performance allows marketers to assess the efficacy of their marketing efforts in relation to their plan's objectives. According to Etuk et al. (2022), marketing performance is the process of harmonising the marketing team's objectives with the tangible outcomes achieved. It is quantified by using measures such as revenues and sales volume, lead creation, customer retention, customer satisfaction, brand awareness, and customer engagement. Zulfikar (2018) illustrates that the evaluation of marketing performance gauges the effectiveness of value creation, achieved through the enhancement of innovation skills and a comprehensive understanding of market orientation.

In this study marketing performance is the organisation's efforts aimed at converting the potential customers to realized customer and retaining such over a period of time through customer relationship and customer satisfaction with a view to maintaining or increasing the customer base and sales volume. It is the totality of the outcomes of the marketer or organization's efforts aimed at attracting new customers and retaining the existing ones with a view to increasing the organisation's customer base, sales volume and profit through quality products/services, customer satisfaction and customer relationship management. Simply put, marketing performance is the realisation of organisation's marketing objectives in the target market. It is measure in terms of market share and customer satisfaction

2.2.1 Market Share

Market share denotes the percentage that a business holds within the total product purchases made by customers (Jorg & Christoph, 2020). This market share can be assessed based on either value or volume. Specifically, value market share is derived from a company's total share compared to overall segment sales, while volume market share pertains to the actual quantity of units sold by a business in relation to the total units sold in the market. When comparing these two metrics, the relationship between value and volume market share is not necessarily linear. In other words, a unit may have a high value but a low quantity, leading to a situation where the value market share is high while the volume market share is low.

Market share evaluates a customer's inclination toward a specific product when compared to alternative options (Adesanya et al., 2018).

Attaining a higher market share provides MSMEs with a competitive edge. MSMEs boasting substantial market shares benefit from advantageous cost prices negotiated with manufacturers due to their significant order volumes, thereby enhancing their purchasing influence (Olubiyi, et al., 2019). An increase in market share implies that, as the market expands, the leader secures a larger portion compared to others. Similarly, a market leader must stimulate market growth to fuel its own expansion. The term "market leader" denotes a product, brand, company, MSMEs, organization, etc., holding the highest percentage of total sales. Strategies for augmenting market share involve initiatives like innovation, cultivating customer relationships (entrepreneurial orientation), implementing effective staffing practices, and outperforming competitors.

2.2.2 Customer Satisfaction

Satisfaction is essentially the sense of contentment or fulfillment derived from a particular experience. Jorg and Christoph (2020) characterize satisfaction as an individual's emotional response, ranging from disappointment to pleasure, arising from a comparison between their perceptions of a product's performance and their initial expectations. Echoing this sentiment, Duru, et al. (2018) elaborate that customer satisfaction involves evaluating the difference between anticipated and perceived performance, assessing the alignment of purchase expectations with actual performance during the consumption of a product or service. Satisfaction is achieved when performance exceeds customer expectations, while dissatisfaction ensues if performance falls short of those expectations.

Customer satisfaction represents a positive emotional state resulting from an overall evaluation of the consumption experience (Olubiyi et al., 2019). It is the outcome of customers assessing how well their expectations align with their actual experience. In cases where the performance of a service surpasses customer expectations, it leads to positive confirmation, thereby enhancing customer satisfaction. Conversely, negative disconfirmation results in dissatisfaction. The concept of customer satisfaction is designed to enhance the long-term financial performance of businesses, positively influence customer loyalty, serve as a forward planner for future purchases, contribute to firms' profitability, enhance market value, and foster positive relationships within the cultural context (Hossain & Ahmed, 2019).

Satisfaction among customers with the products or services offered by MSMEs is commonly perceived as a crucial factor contributing to a company's success and sustained competitiveness over the long term. The concept of customer satisfaction has evolved significantly as a fundamental construct in overseeing and managing activities within the relationship marketing paradigm.

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Oyeku, et al. (2020) assert that customer satisfaction is viewed as a transient emotional state arising from an individual comparison of a customer's expectations with the assessment of a specific product or service interaction.

2.3 Small Business/Enterprise

Small businesses are pivotal to the growth and development of the economy of a nation. Many developed economies have achieved greatness through heavy investment in small and medium enterprises. The term small or medium enterprises has no universally acceptable definition. Small and medium enterprise, small scale industries, and small-scale enterprises have been used interchangeably to mean a small-scale industry. For instance, USAID classified micro enterprise as informal businesses employing five or fewer workers including unpaid family labour; small enterprises as those operating in the formal sector with five to twenty employees; and medium enterprises as those employing 21 to 50 employees (Ayo-Balogun & Ogunsanwo, 2019). Whereas the European Union defined small and medium businesses as any enterprise employing less than 250 employees, and went further to break down the small and medium enterprises into micro (employed less than 10 employees, small (employed between 10 to 49 employees) and medium (employed between 50 to 249 employees).

In Nigeria, the major criteria used in defining small and medium enterprises (SMEs) include number of employees, financial strength, sales value, initial capital outlay, relative size, independent ownership and the type of industry. In view of the above, the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) in its monetary policy circular No 22 of 1988 defined small enterprises as having an annual turnover not exceeding five hundred thousand naira (Ali in Ayo-Balogun & Ogunsanwo, 2019).

According to National Bureau of Statistics (2021); Small and Medium Enterprise Development Agency (2021), small and medium enterprises are those firms or businesses that arise due to entrepreneurial activities of individual who wants to be self-independent and be their own boss by taking risk. Small enterprises are those enterprises with 10 to 49 employees and a turnover greater than ₦25million but less than ₦100million. Medium enterprises are those employing 50 to 199 employees and a turnover greater than ₦100million but less than ₦1billion. Based on the peculiarity of this study and the study area, small businesses are those businesses employing between 5 to 10 employees, with the working capital of ₦10-20 million and annual turnover or gross income of ₦15-25 million.

2.4 Theoretical Framework

Uncertainty-Bearing Theory of Profit which was propounded by Frank H. Knight in 1921 provides the basis for this study. Knight in his book "Risk, Uncertainty and Profit" distinguished between measurable risks (foreseeable risks), which can be estimated in advance and insured against, and true uncertainty (unforeseeable risks) which cannot be quantified, estimated or predicted (Fiorito & McCann 2024). The author argued that entrepreneurs are different from ordinary managers because of their willingness to bear uncertainty in business ventures. The readiness to bear uncertainty differentiates entrepreneurial profit from wages or interest, as it represents the compensation entrepreneurs receive for venturing into unpredictable market conditions.

The main thrust of the theory is that profit is the reward for assuming uncertainty in business decisions. Risks that can be estimated and transferred to others may not earn special rewards, but uncertainties that cannot be insured against create opportunities to earn profits (LToney & Davis, 2023).

The theory is relevant to the study because entrepreneurial risk-taking is inseparable from the growth, competitiveness and market performance of small businesses. Budding entrepreneurs who engage in risk-taking by venturing into new markets, introducing innovative products, or expanding their operations under uncertain conditions are more likely to gain market share and sustain growth (Cyril-Nwuche, 2025). Based on this, the theory provides a solid foundation for examining the link between entrepreneurial calculated risk-taking and market positioning of small enterprises in Ekiti State, Nigeria.

2.5 Empirical Review

In Bayelsa State, Ajour and Nwaiwu (2020) conducted a study investigating the impact of a calculated risk-taking mindset on the organizational sustainability of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSNEs) in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. The research employed a cross-sectional survey with a quasi-experimental design. Results of the data analysis using Spearman Rank Order Correlation Coefficient, revealed a positive and significant relationship between calculated risk-taking mindset and organizational sustainability. Also, Jeje (2020) conducted a study assessing the performance of bakeries in Tanzania in connection with risk-taking. The research employed a multi-stage sampling technique. Principal component factor analysis, qualitative content analysis (manifest analysis), and moderator analysis were utilized for data analysis. Results revealed a significant positive contribution of calculated risk-taking to the performance of bakeries in Tanzania. Similarly, Onyenma et al. (2020) conducted a research examining the correlation between risk-taking and the performance of MSMEs in Rivers and Bayelsa states of Nigeria. Analytical methods employed included Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficients and linear regression analysis. The findings indicated a positive and significant relationship between risk-taking and MSMEs' performance.

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3.0 METHODOLOGY

The research employed a descriptive survey research design. Using systematic and purposive sampling techniques, eight (8) local government areas (LGAs) out of the sixteen LGAs in Ekiti state, Nigeria were selected for the study. The LGAs are Ado, Ekiti East, Ekiti West, Gbonyin, Ijero, Ikole, Irepodun/Ifelodun and Moba from which the sample were drawn. These LGAs were selected because they have the highest number of registered small businesses in the State. With the aid of proportionate sampling technique, 99, 35, 37, 29, 34, 62, 23 and 64 small businesses were selected from the eight previously selected LGAs respectively, totaling 383. Primary data used for the study were collected with the aid of semi-structured questionnaire and analysed using means, standard deviation and multiple regression.

3.1 Model Specification

Multiple regression was adopted to achieve the objective of the study. Mathematically, the regression model was developed as:

$$MPF = f(CLR) \dots\dots\dots 1$$

$$CLR = f(ENM, ANT, FRK, NVD, SFD, CFC) \dots\dots\dots 2$$

Where:

MPF= Marketing Performance (Dependent Variable)

CLR = Calculated Risk (Independent Variable)

ENM = Entering New Market

ANT= Adoption of New Technology

FRK = Financial Risk

NVD = New Venture Development

SFD = Source of Funding

CFC= Credit Facilities to Customer

Mathematically, the regression equation is expressed as:

$$MPF = \alpha + \beta_1ENM + \beta_2ANT + \beta_3FRK + \beta_4NVD + \beta_5SFD+ \beta_6CFC + \mu \dots\dots\dots 3$$

Where:

MPF = Market Performance (Dependent Variable)

ENM = Entering New Market

ANT= Adoption of New Technology

FRK = Financial Risk

NVD = New Venture Development

SFD = Source of Funding

CFC= Credit Facilities to Customer

α = Constant

μ = Stochastic/Error Term

$\beta_1 - \beta_6$ = Gradient of the Slope

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Respondents Perception on Calculated Risk-taking and Marketing Performance

S/N	Statement	Mean	SD	Remark
1	As a small business owner, I have inclination to enter new market.	4.69	0.559	Agree
2	Adoption of new technologies always give me an edge over competitors	4.26	0.653	Agree
3	Always willing to commit my money or capital to a business I am interested in.	4.28	0.698	Agree
4	Despite the uncertainty, I like to be a first timer in a new market to exploit opportunities.	4.10	0.924	Agree
5	I exploit all available sources of funding when I perceived a business to be lucrative.	4.21	0.812	Agree
6	I extend credit facilities to my customers	3.98	1.008	Agree
	Grand Mean	4.25	0.776	Agree

Source: Field Survey (2025)

Table 1 presents the average responses of the respondents to each statement in the research instrument. The mean scores for all statements consistently exceeded 3.0, leading to the decision recorded in the final column of the table. The analysis from the table indicates a strong affirmation from the respondents regarding the impact of calculated risk-taking on the marketing performance of

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small businesses in Ekiti State, Nigeria. The participants agreed that calculated risk-taking significantly contributed to the success of their respective businesses. Moreover, the respondents recognized that calculated risk-taking plays a crucial role in the success of organizations. The overall evaluation of the function of calculated risk-taking yielded a grand mean of 4.25.

4.1 Test of Hypothesis

H₀: Calculated risk-taking has no significant effect on the marketing performance of small businesses in Ekiti State, Nigeria

Table 2a: Calculated risk-taking and marketing performance of Small Enterprise

Model	R	R ²	Adj R ²	B	Std Error	T value	P Value
	0.413	0.271	0.266				
Calculated risk-taking and Performance				.479	.083	5.762	.000
Constant				2.042	.357	5.722	.000
F cal= 33.196 F tab = 1.960							

Source: Data Analysis (2025)

Table 2b: Model Summary

Model	Change Statistics		
	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	1 ^a	161	.000

Source: Data Analysis (2025)

a. Predictors: (Constant), Calculated risk-taking

Table 2c: ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	23.827	1	23.827	33.196	.000 ^b
	Residual	115.559	161	.718		
	Total	139.387	162			

Source: Data Analysis (2025)

a. Dependent Variable: Market Perf

b. Predictors: (Constant), Calculated risk-taking

Table 2d: Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.042	.357		5.722	.000
	Calculated risk-taking	.479	.083	.413	5.762	.000

Source: Data Analysis (2025)

a. Dependent Variable: Calculated risk-taking

The objective of the study focuses on calculated risk-taking and its effects on the marketing performance of small businesses in Ekiti State, Nigeria was tested with the aid of multiple regression analysis. As outlined in Tables 2a-2d, the regression coefficient between small businesses' marketing performance and the explanatory variable (calculated risk-taking) displayed a positive value of 0.413. This suggests that calculated risk-taking exerts a moderately positive influence on marketing performance of small businesses, indicating a favourable effect of the explanatory variable. The coefficient of determination (R²)= 0.271, signifies that the explanatory variable (calculated risk-taking) accounted for 27.1% of the variation in marketing performance of small businesses. The remaining 72.9% of the variation is attributable to stochastic variables or other factors not considered in the study. The adjusted R² further corroborates these findings, registering a coefficient of 0.266. This value (R²= 0.266) indicated the actual contribution of the explanatory variable (calculated risk-taking) 26.6% to marketing performance of small businesses.

Table 2d displays the unstandardized β coefficient for calculated risk-taking, revealing a positive value of 0.479 with a t-value of 5.762; P= 0.000. This outcome indicates a highly significant effect of calculated risk-taking on the marketing performance of small

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businesses, establishing its statistical significance. The positive relationship between calculated risk-taking and small businesses' performance suggests that respondents' rationale for marketing performance is strongly and positively influenced by their willingness to take calculated risks. Consequently, owners or managers of small businesses are inclined to pursue high-risk ventures, take bold initiatives to achieve objectives, and are encouraged to undertake calculated risks associated with new ideas.

The F-test is employed to assess the overall significance of the model by comparing the calculated F-value with the tabulated F-value, as outlined in Table 2a. The table indicates that the calculated F-value exceeded the tabulated F-value. Therefore, the alternate hypothesis is accepted, and the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that calculated risk-taking significantly influences the marketing performance of small businesses in Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Therefore, the regression line is stated as marketing performance = $2.042 + 0.479Crt$

4.2 Discussion of Findings

The effects of calculated risk-taking on the marketing performance of small business was assessed through multiple regression analysis. The results revealed a moderate but significant association between calculated risk-taking and the marketing performance of small businesses in Ekiti State, Nigeria. The acceptance of the alternate hypothesis and rejection of the null hypothesis supported the findings that calculated risk-taking is both significant and positively correlated with the marketing performance of small businesses in Ekiti State, Nigeria.

This findings of the study aligns with the research conducted by Ajor and Nwaiwu (2020), who explored the impact of a risk-taking mindset on organizational sustainability of SMEs in Bayelsa State, Nigeria, using a cross-sectional survey and Spearman Rank Order Correlation. Their analysis demonstrated a positive and significant relationship between a risk-taking mindset and organizational sustainability across all LGAs in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. Similarly, Yahaya, et al. (2021) investigated the influence of risk-taking competencies on SMEs using percentages and multiple regression analysis. Their study found that risk-taking competencies have a positive and significant effect on the survival of SMEs in Nigeria.

Similarly, the outcomes of the study corroborates the results of a study conducted by Kitigin (2017), which established a positive and significant relationship between calculated risk-taking and business performance. In addition, the findings is in line with the results of the study by Baba and Thiong (2019) which indicated that calculated risk-taking has a positive and significant effect on the performance of MSMEs in Nigeria. However, it deviates from the findings of Olaniran et al. (2016), who reported a negative relationship between calculated risk-taking and returns on assets.

5.0 CONCLUSION AND MANAGERIAL IMPLICATIONS

Based on the findings, the study concludes that a unit increase in calculated risk-taking led to a significant and positive adjustment in marketing performance of small businesses generally. Deliberately taking calculated risk by small businesses in the face of uncertainty yields positive results and significant improvement in their marketing performance. It is therefore expedient for small business owners to note that the higher the risk the more profitable the reward is. They should endeavour to enter new markets and be the first timer. It is equally important to extend credit facilities to their customers and considering adopting new technologies or inventions as soon as they are available so as to match competition in their respective sector. There are many new markets begging for attention from small business owners, entering such a market and starting a new venture there will be more rewarding that competing in an over saturated market. Small business owners should try to improve on their customer satisfaction efforts with a view to increasing their market share. All attempts should be made to attract new customers, retain the existing ones and convert them to loyal customers. This will enable the small businesses to expand their customer base and compete favourably in the market.

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